

Assessing The Teaching Quality of Physical and Health Education Teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in Lagos State Nigeria

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Abstract

The quality of teaching has become a prominent issue in the area of physical and health education due to the new trends in teaching pedagogy, assessment, aids, modes and the content of the curriculum. However, the teaching quality of physical and health education can be determined using co-variables such as the curriculum content knowledge, reflections and subject status. This study therefore assessed the teaching quality of Physical and health education Teachers in Junior Secondary School in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. All the Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV consisting of Apapa, Surulere and Mainland Local Government Areas were covered in the study. Two hundred and thirty-Five Physical and health education Teachers were purposively sampled for the study. A standardized questionnaire with reliability co-efficient of 0.83 was used as an instrument to collect data for the study. Three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of Significance. Data collected were subjected to frequency counts and percentages and inferential statistics of chi-square. The study established that two of the hypotheses were rejected except for one, and eleven respondent's mortality was recorded in the study. There was a significant influence of the co-variables on the teaching quality of physical and health education in junior secondary schools in education district IV. it is therefore recommended that among others that upgrading teacher's knowledge or physical and health education will be an added advantage of the subject and this can be achieved by internship trainings and courses in other to maintain a standard level.

Keywords: Teaching quality, physical education, health education, teachers and junior secondary schools.

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Introduction

Teacher quality is fundamental to understanding the role of licensure tests in promoting it. It suggests that the knowledge and techniques used by competent teachers are many and varied. To learn whether or how licensure tests might promote teacher quality, it is important to distinguish teacher quality from teaching quality. States and local districts play an important role in promoting teaching quality. If schools are not well organized and supportive, it is possible that even good teachers will not be successful (Raudenbush and Bryk, 2002). Successful teaching depends on many factors, including the curriculum contents, teacher's reflection, level of instructional resources available, staffing levels, continuing professional development, subject status and support from administrators and parents (Aiyejuyo, 2002). The school and community forces that shape teachers' practices and student learning are numerous and important. Quality teaching is doing whatever it takes, ethnically and responsibly, to ensure that students learn, and that they leave the unit with a passion for learning. Many of us have had the experience of having at least one great teacher, changes are that you are being challenged to learn, and believed that you could achieve. They were possibly also enthusiastically passionate about learning, and didn't take themselves too seriously (Macquire, 2015). Teaching is first and foremost a cultural activity, and notions of teacher quality have changed over time as western society has shifted its values and concerns. Moreover, in any given time, different individuals and groups can hold very different ideas about teacher quality. A review of past definitions of teacher quality can provide as context for understanding contemporary definitions. One popular criterion for teacher quality is high moral character. Teachers are often expected to be good role models for students and to represent the highest standards of social propriety. This view of teacher quality was especially widespread in the early 1900s. At that time, teachers were often placed on pedestals so to speak, as were ministers. When a teacher entered a room, people stopped talking and became self conscious and embarrassed. A definition of teacher quality emphasizes a broader range of personality and character traits-such as curiosity, enthusiasm, and compassion. Interest in personality traits were especially widespread in the decades immediately following World War II partly in response to popular psychoanalytical theories and partly in response for concerns that America needed to ensure that it would not be susceptible to the totalitarian influences that had captivated other countries. Another definition of teacher quality focuses on teacher's skills rather than their morality or personality traits. This approach to teacher quality was especially widespread in the post-Sputnik era when American policy makers sponsored numerous curriculum design efforts and wanted teachers to implement the programs exactly as specified. Pursuing the idea of the teacher with technical skills, researchers in the next decades focused

on observing teachers in their classrooms, at first to see how well they were implementing specific curricula and later to document specific teaching practices that seemed to be associated with gains in students' test scores (Brophy & Good, 2009). This latter body of work focused on discrete practices such as questioning and lesson pacing. This research came to be known as "process-product" research, since it sought relationships between classroom processes and the product of gains in student achievement. This movement marked the first time that student achievement became a widely criterion for teacher quality. The goal of this research was to identify specific behaviors that other teachers could emulate. Researchers focused on such skills as question asking, lesson pacing, and clarity in explanations. The greatest challenge facing the physical and health education teacher is the task of teaching motor skills and sport-related concepts to students. Sidentop (1992) pointed out "regardless of one's political orientations, personal background, or professional training, it is imperative that a sport pedagogist possesses the qualities and skills necessary to increase someone's knowledge and proficiency in physical activity". In doing this, teachers must exhibit a sense of direction in their teaching and also be effective. An understanding of what constitutes good and effective teaching is vital to the work of the teacher. It is not hard for most of us to recall the "good teachers" who taught us over the years. They must have taught us something to make us feel important or value ourselves, or may have even served as a friend, counselor, or been a challenging or entertaining pedagogue. In this sense, 'good' teaching is a personal definition that most of us hold and "effective teachers" taught us in a way that we learned new skills (Adegbamigbe, 2002). On the other hand, the use of *teaching quality* while referring to universities and further education contexts implies that the quality has to do with *how* a teacher is teaching. So if there is a problem with quality, it is not a problem with the teachers themselves but with the teaching methods or curriculum they are using (Apara, et al., 2022). However, the subject of this research is narrowed down to the teaching of sports and physical and health education in secondary schools in Lagos, Nigeria. Obviously, the dynamism in the field of Physical and health education and Sports itself is fundamentally expected in any growing profession. The teacher quality in relation to teaching quality is subject to many variables including the curriculum which can be featured into what makes a good teaching (Aiyejuyo 2014). The major focus of curriculum framework is to clarify the educational orientation which will serve as driving force for future curriculum development and implementation (Drapper, 1986). Differing philosophical orientation towards education are the result of different values and beliefs about education, the learner and society. Any attempt to develop curricular must clarify and make explicit these particular values and beliefs. Clarification of values and beliefs can also assist school boards, schools and teachers in adapting programs that affect the

uniqueness of their school and community. The clarification of broadly held belief about education subsequently determines the extent to which a curriculum framework elicits the participation and support of other stakeholders in the creation of curricula. Adjusting the focus, and the curriculum models it describes, encourages curriculum developers to combine strong theoretical background with personal knowledge of local conditions to create curricular which can be implemented in a variety of local contexts that contains teacher's reflective acts. The curriculum framework also provides sufficient flexibility to permit teachers to adapt the curriculum for specific, local physical and health education needs. Jewett and Bain (1985) outline seven physical and health education curriculum models which are currently in use. These models represent widely different perspectives on the place of physical and health education in the educational system, based on differing views of the learner, learning, educational intentions and fundamental beliefs about the role of schools in society. The Personal-Global orientation to physical and health education requires a combination of its models in the implementation of a Personal-Global curriculum. Within the Personal-Global Curriculum Framework, teachers may adapt one or more of Jewett and Bain's (1985) to best fit their local school context. Teachers and school districts are best able to determine the means of fulfilling the curriculum intentions outlined in this framework; they are able to adapt and implement curriculum models which best serve the needs of the local school-community environment. Decisions related to such areas as resource allocation, instructional strategies and activity choices which are locally determined, and implemented based on the particular needs and priorities of the school-community. Curriculum models should therefore be combined or modified to provide a curriculum that suits the particular characteristics of the school-community. An analysis of the various models and their potential application to Junior School Physical and health education are outlined in various literatures. A curriculum model which has the potential to meet the needs of Junior students of physical and health education, is the Humanistic Model proposed by Hellison (1991). Jewett and Bain (1985) describe humanistic physical and health education which uses physical activity to assist the student in the search for personal identity. It places "student self-esteem, self-actualization, self-understanding and interpersonal relations at the centre of the physical and health education teaching-learning act". (Hellison, 1991). The teacher does not prescribe and direct learning activities, but facilitates and counsels the student involved in self-directed learning which precipitates the teacher's reflection afterwards.

Research Hypotheses

In structuring this study to address the identified problems, three research hypotheses were developed and tested in the study. The research hypotheses tested in the study were:

1. Curriculum content knowledge will not be a significant factor to assess the teaching quality of physical and health education in Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. Teacher's reflection will not be a significant factor for an assessing the teaching quality of physical and health education in Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV in Lagos State, Nigeria.
3. Physical and health education Status will not be a significant factor for assessing the teaching quality of the subject in Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV in Lagos State, Nigeria.

METHODS

Research Model:

The Descriptive survey research design was used for the study.

Population Sample:

The Population-Sample comprised of 235 Physical and Health Education teachers in Education district IV, which comprised of three Local Government Areas in Lagos State, Nigeria. A purposive random sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents for the study.

Data Collection Tools:

The instrument used for the study was a self-developed structured questionnaire modified from a standardized instrument validated by experts in the field of physical, health education and counseling. The questionnaire consisted of co-variates relating to curriculum content area, teacher's reflection and subject status.

Data Collection:

Data was collected on personal basis using one of the teachers as a coordinator in each school. The purpose, importance, and relevance of the study were explained to the participants during our routine meetings with them after an official permission was sought for from the school district head to carry out a research. A voice message was also sent to their various platforms, and informed consent was obtained for their participation. All the participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and identity.

Data Analysis

The descriptive statistics of charts and frequency counts was used to analyze the demographic data of participants, while the inferential statistics of Chi-square was used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

FINDINGS

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Female	132	41.1
Male	92	59.0
Qualification		
N.C.E	62	27.7
B.Sc/B.A/B.Ed	121	54.0
M.Sc/M.A/M.Ed	41	18.0

When Table 1 is examined, it shows the chart distribution of gender with male recording a range of 41.1% while female recorded a wide range of 59.0% respectively. The distribution of respondents according to qualification, 62 (27.7%) of the respondents have NCE as their qualification, 121 (54.0%) of the respondents fall within the B.Sc/B.A/B.Ed level certificate holders, while 41(18.0%) fall within the M.Sc/M.A/M.Ed category; none of the respondents had other class of certificate.

Table 2: Showing analysis of Curriculum Content Knowledge of Respondents

Variable	X ² crit	X ² cal	df	P<
Curriculum Content Knowledge	43.7729	138.4	39	0.05

*P<0.5

Table 2 shows analysis of the results using a Chi square (X²) statistics, which showed a value of 138.4, while the Table value is 43.7729 at a df of 39 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, since the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value with a significant difference this shows that the hypothesis which states Curriculum content knowledge will not be a significant factor for assessing the teaching quality of Physical and Health Education teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected.

Table 2: Showing Chi-Square analysis of Teacher Reflection

Variable	X ² crit	X ² cal	df	P<
Teachers Reflection	67.5048	588.211	51	0.05

*P<0.5

Table 2 shows analysis of the results using a Chi square (X²) statistics, which showed a value of 588.211, while the Table value is 67.5048 at a degree of freedom of 51 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the Table value with a significant difference this shows that the hypothesis which states that Teachers reflection will not be a significant factor for a assessing the teaching quality of the subject in Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV in Lagos State, Nigeria is hereby rejected.

Table 3: Showing Chi-Square analysis of Status of Physical and Health Education teaching in the School

Variable	X ² crit	X ² cal	df	P<
Status of Physical and health education Teaching in the School	40.1133	23.20	27	0.05

*P<0.5

Table 3 shows analysis of the results using a Chi square (X²) statistics, which showed a value of 23.20, while the table value is 40.1133 at a df of 27 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated Chi-square value is lesser than the table value with a significant difference this shows that the hypothesis which states that Physical and health education Status will not be a significant factor for assessing the teaching quality of the subject in Junior Secondary Schools in Education District IV in Lagos State, Nigeria is not rejected.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Results showed that there is a significant effect on the teaching quality of junior secondary school Physical and Health Education teachers in Lagos State, Nigeria. The differences is found to be significantly high because most Physical and Health Education teachers in Lagos State Junior secondary schools are professionals and well trained in their cognate areas unlike the private schools where non-professional are used to teach, and even teach outside their area of specialization. This finding is in line with the findings of Jowett and Bain (1985) who described humanistic physical and health education as an act which uses physical activity to assist students in the search for personal identity and confidence. Furthermore, he also stated that this practice thus helps to discover teachers and student's self-esteem, self-actualization, self understanding and interpersonal relationship. In corroboration, Resnick (1987), Leinhardt and Greeno (1986), Wilson, Shulman and Richert (1988) stated that planning and teaching any subject including physical and health education is a highly complex cognitive activity in which the teacher must apply knowledge from multiple domains. In contrary to the above findings,

Akindutire and Olanipekun (2012) in their observation stated that physical and health education has suffered neglect in Nigerian educational institutions in the past, as its scope was only limited to exercise, physical drills or muscle building. More so, Adedeji (1985) and Ojeme (1990) all observed that the framework of Physical and Health Education includes forms of movement, mechanical principles of movement, structure and function of man in motion, methodological dimension of human movement among others which a trained and certified physical and health education teacher must possess.

In this finding, teachers' reflection was observed to be effective on the quality of teaching. The finding is in line with the concept of teacher belief system, its practices and attitudes which are important for understanding and improving educational processes. According to Brophy and Good (2009); in their write-up observed that the aspect of teacher's reflection and practice are related to effective classroom learning and student's outcomes. They further stated that generally, teacher's reflection when consist of close monitoring, adequate pacing, classroom management, well structured lessons, clarity of presentations and informatics feedback have been shown to have a positive impact on student's achievement and teacher's delivery system. In corroboration, Shulman (2007) stated that professional competence is believed to be a crucial factor of teacher's reflection and commitment in classroom teaching and school practices. In addition to knowing about the subject matter, theories of learning and teaching among teachers should aim at improving their ability to put all this knowledge into practice thereby becoming more skillful at teaching. Teacher's reflection and commitment to teaching can be further developed by increasing self-awareness using audio or video tape of their lessons thus watch, analyze and reflect on their recordings. More so, teaching a colleague and asking them for feedback after the lesson may also help build up such skills and also observing other teachers teach, can foster unity of teacher's reflection and commitment which can be very enlightening thus comparing teaching styles and practices.

The third hypotheses were rejected which indicates that the status of the subject is gradually dropping, this was stated by Apalara, et al., (2022) in their findings, since the merger, PHE as a subject has been denied its much needed space in the curriculum, then it may take little or no time for the subject to be deleted or completely subsumed under another subject, and this will cause more harm to the propagation of preventive health care services. Ajisafe (1997) in his study stated that inadequate allocation of time, modern sports facilities, lack of application of educationally sound curriculum, construction methods etc are all constraints in boosting of the subject as a recognizable and compulsory one in Nigerian schools. He further stated that effective teaching skills and learning strategies are the merits of proper learning and

management which will boost the status of the subject, and is possibly visible only when good planning and management take place.

The study concludes that the curriculum contents is effective for the factual assessment of the subject and its revisiting wil boost the status of the subject that is gradually drooping in schools and for this to be effective teacher's reflective ideas will be necessary for revamping the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Upgrading teacher knowledge in PHE will be an added advantage of the subject, therefore, there is need for an immediate action by government and concerned stakeholders to constantly send Physical and health education teachers on internship trainings and courses in order to maintain the level observed and even beyond.
2. Motivating and encouraging teachers' delivery will help to achieve a concrete balance in the field of Physical and health education. Therefore, there is the need for the remuneration package of PHE teachers to be reviewed in all allowances since they double as both teachers and coaches in their various schools.
3. Non-Governmental Organizations and co-operate organizations should assist in providing simple and basic sports equipment and facilities to schools in order to help in teaching practical skills and techniques to students, thereby, promoting future sportsmen and athletes that may win laurel for the country.
4. The adage which says prevention is better than cure should be upheld in this present day. In other words, there is the need to include Physical and health education in all curricula in Nigeria and at all levels, in order to raise the level of awareness in the society about its multiple benefits and encourage practical participation particularly among teachers, students, school managers, policy makers, education experts, local leaders and the public at large.
5. The study had its focus fundamentally on strategies of improving teaching qualities of Physical and health education teachers in Nigeria secondary schools. The findings could not provide the end to the solutions, hence further studies on similar subject matter are recommended.

Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest between the authors.

Statement of Contribution of Researchers:

1. Author: 17%- Initiated the idea and the research, wrote the introduction structured the questionnaire.
2. Author: 15%- Organized the literatures, edited them and adopted the relevant ones
3. Author: 12%-Contributed in the area of literature review, instrument administration and discussion of findings.
4. Author: 9%- Contributed in the area of literature review, methodology and instrument administration.
5. Author: 9%- Contributed in the area of literature review and instrument administration
6. Author: 8%- Contributed in the area of literature review.
7. Author: 9%- Contributed in the area of literature review and instrument administration
8. Author: 8%- Contributed in the area of literature review and instrument administration
9. Author: 13%- Contributed in the area of literature review and instrument administration, collated the collected data and carried out the analysis.

Information about the Ethics Committee Permission: Responsibility for any violations that may arise in the work done belongs to the author.

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